

Effects of deep placement of urea by reflooding water.^a CNRRI experimental farm, Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Application method	Urea N applied (kg N/ha)				Grain yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (%)	N uptake (kg/ha)	Utilization (%) of applied urea N	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
	BT ^b	10 DT ^c	30 DT ^c	Total					
Control	0	0	0	0	6.6 c	6.74	93 c	0	71
Surface broadcast	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.2 b	7.66	129 b	32 d	55
Deepplaced by water	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.4 a	7.78	145 ab	46 b	51
Surface broadcast	67.5	33.75	33.75	135.0	7.4 a	7.62	148 ab	41 c	50
Deepplaced by water	28.3	56.25	28.20	112.5	7.4 a	7.74	149 a	50 a	50

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bBefore transplanting. ^cDays after transplanting.

Potassium nutrition of rice

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We studied K nutrition of rice in a pot experiment using poor-fertility loam soil: 0.56% organic matter, 0.045% N, 1.8% P, 61 ppm K, pH 8.3, and EC 0.6 mmho/cm. Treatments are in the table.

Twentyday-old Basmati 370 seedlings were used. Half were dipped in 0.7% K₂SO₄ solution and half in distilled water. Fertilizer was 100 kg N and 44 kg P/ha.

Dipping seedling roots in a 0.7% solution of K₂SO₄ for 72 h before

Effect of K application method on rice growth, yield, and K concentration.^a Islamabad, Pakistan.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)	K concentration (mg/g)	
					Straw	Grain
Control	121.3 b	6.4 c	46.1 c	20.2 c	10.90 a	6.76 b
166 kg K/ha	124.0 b	13.3 b	49.9 bc	21.5 c	11.81 a	13.88 a
0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	132.3 a	16.0 a	61.7 a	29.5 a	13.10 a	17.03 a
166 kg K/ha +0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	126.0 ab	12.7 b	55.4 b	25.6 b	13.90 a	13.39 a
LSD (0.05)	7	2.5	11.1	3.5	4.4	

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

transplanting resulted in significantly taller plants, more of productive tillers per plant, and higher straw and grain yield. K concentration in straw was not significantly affected by the treatments, but K application method affected K

concentration in rice grain. When 166 kg K/ha was applied with root dipping, plant height, productive tillers, and straw and grain yield were slightly lower. □

Breaking dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

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In an attempt to multiply seeds of *S. rostrata*, we planted on 19 Jun 1986 and harvested mature pods on 3 Nov 1986. In Mar 1987, practically no germination of seeds occurred, indicating the existence of dormancy. Attempts were made to break dormancy. Fifty seeds per treatment were arranged on soaked germination paper and kept in a germinator (25 °C). Germination was recorded daily to 7 d after treatment.

Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid

Germination of seeds of *Sesbania rostrata* as affected by various treatments. Dharwad, India, 1986.

Treatment	Germination (%)
Control	0
Hot water (60 °C for 5 min)	4
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃ 0.1%)	8
Sand scarification	8
Overnight soaking in water	12
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 20 min	28
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 25 min	44
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 30 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 35 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 40 min	96

was most effective in breaking dormancy (see table). However, there was considerable variation in

germination with time of treatment. Germination increased from 28% with 20 min to 96% with 40 min. □

Influence of paclobutrazol on rice seedling growth

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Rice Bai You Zhan No. 33 seedling growth was influenced by a soil drench of paclobutrazol granules at the one-leaf stage. Treated seedlings had faster leaf growth, shorter and stronger seedlings, higher tiller numbers, richer chlorophyll content, stronger rooting ability, and somewhat greater chilling resistance (see table). □

Effect of paclobutrazol on rice seedling growth^a, Gungzhou, China.

Treatment ^b (g/m ²)	Shoot ht (cm)	Width of false stem (cm)	% of seedlings with				Chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)			Rooting ability ^c (mg/plant)	
			No tiller	1 tiller	2 tillers	3 tillers	Chla	Chlb	a+b	Fresh wt of root	Dry wt of root
0	26.5	0.2	73.3	26.7	0	0	0.66	0.36	1.01	60.8	5.9
1.67	22.3	0.3	46.7	16.7	30.7	6.7	0.97	0.46	1.43	65.6	8.0
3.34	21.2	0.3	40.0	26.7	23.3	10.0	1.06	0.51	1.57	76.5	8.2

^aAt four-leaf stage. ^bGranules containing 0.6% paclobutrazol. ^cNew root growth after total removal of old roots.

Impact of level and source of slow-release N fertilizers on rice yield and yield components

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We evaluated four levels of N applied as prilled urea (PU), rock phosphate-coated urea (RPCU, 31.2% N), and gypsum-coated urea (GCU, 32.2% N) during 1986 wet season. The experimental site has pH 5.5, EC 0.2 dS/m, 0.48% organic C, 24.2 kg P/ha, 49.8 kg K/ha, 0.78 ppm Zn, 1.71 ppm Cu, 40.95 ppm Fe, 0.65 ppm Mn, and 0.74 ppm B. The experiment was laid out in split-plot design.

Three 28-d-old IET3232 medium-duration seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 15 cm spacing 23 Jul 1986. PU was applied 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Recommended 35 kg P, 73 kg K/ha, RPCU, and GCU

Effect of N source and level on grain yield and yield components of rice. ^a Mangalore, India, 1986.

Treatment	Plant height 40 DP (m)	Plant height at harvest (cm)	Tiller 40 DP (av no.)	Productive tillers at harvest (no.)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	1000- grain wt (g)	Straw yield (t/ha)
<i>Level (kg N/ha)</i>								
No N	56	81	10	8	260	4.8	21.9	4.6
37.5	64	85	12	9	312	5.1	21.8	5.8
75.0	69	90	12	10	327	5.1	22.0	(6.4)
112.5	72	89	14	9	321	5.2	22.0	7.0
CD (0.05)	6	2	2	1	24	0.2	ns	1.0
CV (%)	7	2	18	10	7	5.9	3.7	22.0
<i>Sources (S)</i>								
PU	62	87	12	9	295	5.1	22.0	5.9
RPCU	67	87	12	9	319	5.2	22.0	5.6
GCU	67	86	12	9	301	4.9	22.0	6.4
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.2	ns	ns
CV (%)	8	2	16	6	8	6.3	3.2	25.0
Interaction (L × S)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a DP = days after planting.

were applied basally. The field was flooded from transplanting to harvest and the crop protected from insects, diseases, and weeds. Harvest was 12 Nov 1986.

All yield components but 1,000-grain

weight showed a significant response to N level (see table). But responses to N sources were not similar in all characters. Slow-release N fertilizers at low levels increased grain yield in the high rainfall areas of Mangalore. □

Chemical analyses and thermal studies of azolla

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Azolla, recognized as a natural nitrogenous fertilizer for rice, barley, rye, and wheat crops, also has been recommended as a food additive in animal feeds. We report here trace element content, calorific value, and thermal decomposition studies.

Azolla pinnata and *A. microphylla* samples were collected from IRRI

ricefields, washed with distilled water, and air-dried. Trace elements were analyzed using Pye Unicam 281 and Shimadzu AA 630-01 atomic absorption spectrophotometers. X-ray fluorescence spectra were recorded on Geigerflex 3064 using Rb target (supplied by M/s. Rgaku Corporation, Japan). N analysis was done by Kjeldahl method. Calorific value was determined using Parr bomb calorimeter with correction for S. TG and DTA were recorded on Shimadzu-DT 30 simultaneous thermal analyzer.

X-ray fluorescence analysis indicated the presence of several trace elements essential for animals and plants (see

table). Quantitative analysis revealed the absence of lead, mercury, and arsenic in azolla, indicating its safety as a fodder. The heavier elements are not detected because of limitations of the target employed.

The presence of N, phosphate, and essential elements suggests azolla as a molybdenum supplement to animal feed, especially for mammalian animals such as cattle. Its calorific value of 4.84 kcal/g indicates that azolla is actively involved in metabolic pathways.

TG and DTA studies indicated that in air, azolla undergoes decomposition in four stages. In the first stage, moisture